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Employability and the knowledge, skills and competencies of engineering graduates
Case Study of Finnish Engineering Education

ABSTRACT

This system paper will examine the amount and quality of work experience of newly graduated Finnish professionals from the field of technology and the knowledge, skills and competencies that the graduates have gained through formal engineering studies and through work experience gained during studies.

In the future world of work the ability to adopt and to apply new knowledge are crucial skills and enable life-long learning. New learning models such as problem-based learning, project-based learning, co-ops and CDIO are needed in providing engineers with skills and competencies they can utilize throughout their career. As the graduates have a significant amount of work experience it allows the universities to utilize the work experience and to recognize the competencies the students have gained outside the classroom.

Conference Key Areas: Skills and Engineering Education

Keywords: employability, work experience, graduates, skills

1 INTRODUCTION

Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland - TEK is a service and labour market organization for professionals and students in the area of engineering and technology. The 73 000 members of TEK mostly hold a M.Sc. degree in engineering, technology, architecture or natural sciences. In addition to labour market issues, TEK actively participates in the developing engineering education and further professional development. TEK works in close collaboration with universities, political authorities, representatives of working life and other relevant stakeholders. One of the main interests for TEK is to make sure that the Finnish Universities of Engineering and Technology will have the best possible funding and framework to provide top quality engineering education.

One of the practical tools used for monitoring the quality of engineering education is Graduate Feedback Survey which is directed at newly graduated M.Sc. engineers and architects. TEK and the Finnish universities of higher engineering education have conducted this joint feedback survey on a national scale for graduates since 2011. The main purpose of the feedback survey is to gather comparable information on the quality of the Finnish engineering M.Sc. degrees. Some highlights of the areas the survey covers are the quality of formal studies, the skills, competencies and knowledge gained by the graduates and their employment after graduation. This graduate feedback survey covers over 95 per cent of the Finnish M.Sc. engineering graduates. In 2016 the response rate was as high as 68 %.

In Finnish higher education it is rather typical that students gain a significant amount of work experience in industry during their studies. On average a graduate in the field of engineering and technology has more than 2 years of work experience of which 8 months is study related and equivalent to graduates level of education. Typically also the master thesis is done in industry which means that graduates have a strong professional network already at the time of graduation and they have demonstrated the ability to apply theory into practice.

This paper will present some recent findings from the data regarding employability and the knowledge skills and competencies the students gain from their studies and the work experience they gain during their studies.

2 THE FINNISH HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

2.1 The Finnish higher education system in the field of engineering and technology

Finnish higher education system is based on a dual/binary system of higher education. The higher education institutions constitute of universities and universities of applied sciences (UAS). The members of TEK include professionals with at least second cycle university level degrees and students currently studying for second cycle degrees. Seven out of fourteen Finnish universities provide studies in the field of engineering and technology.

Finnish higher education system is not governed by any strategic policy papers per se at the moment as the policy paper system of higher education is currently under reform. The latest of the strategic policy papers called *koulutuksen ja tutkimuksen*

kehityssuunnitelma KESU (education and research development plan) covered the development of higher education up until 2016. Currently the strategic goals of higher education are defined only in the government programme of 2015-2019 with four main goals for higher education: enhancing student selection processes, year-round study possibilities, digital learning environments and reviewing the eligibility demands in public positions.

Finnish higher education policy has aimed for decreasing length of studies for more than a decade. Regarding statutory developments, university students used to have unlimited time to complete their studies which has been limited to seven years since 2006. The public funding of universities is also strongly governing to faster completion of studies with amount of students achieving degrees and at least 55 study credits per academic year being rewarded generously. The universities are also governed for decreasing study times through university-specific negotiations arranged every four years.

The government policies aiming for shorter study times are justified with the aim to increase the amount of time population is active in the labour market. The long study times of Finnish students however seems not to decrease the length of careers at least in the field of technology: the study times lengthen mostly because the students are very active in the labour market already during studies. The culture of working alongside studies is also very beneficial for the students as explored further in this paper.

2.2 Monitoring the output: Graduate Feedback Survey

The graduate feedback survey discussed in this paper is a joint effort of TEK and those Finnish universities which provide education in the field of engineering and technology. The survey has been conducted since 2011 and it covers over 95 % of all graduates from academic studies in the field of engineering and technology. The response rate of the survey is very high, for example in 2015 the response rate was as high as 72 % of all graduates and in 2016 the responserate was 68 %. The survey is yearly open from the beginning of January until the end of December. The survey is rather extensive with 56 overall questions and an estimated response time of 45 minutes.

2.3 Culture of working along studies in Finland

Gaining work experience while studying is very typical in Finnish higher education system and Finnish labour market. Working during studies serves many functions for the students. First of all, the financial aid provided for students by the government is in many cases not enough to cover living costs. Secondly working during studies is regarded as a great way of enhancing ones skills, competencies and knowledge. Third, work experience is highly valued in the Finnish labour market, even if the experience is not from the field of studies or does not match the level of education. Work experience from ones own field of science also provides valuable contacts and networks to possible future employers. (TEK opiskelijatutkimus 2016) The percentage of employed university level students are presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Percentage of employed bachelor and master level students by field of education in 2015. (statistics Finland)

3 SKILLS, COMPETENCIES AND KNOWLEDGE GAINED IN STUDIES AND WORK EXPERIENCE

The skills, competencies and knowledge of Finnish graduates in the field of engineering and technology develop both through formal education and work experience gained during studies. The TEK Graduate Survey the development of 26 categorized skills, competencies and knowledge through both formal education and work experience. The results of the 2016 survey are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Self-evaluated development of skills, competencies and knowledge of M.Sc. in

Tech graduates through formal education and work experience gained during studies in 2016. (TEK Graduate Survey 2016)

The differences in development of skills, competencies and knowledge however seem to emphasize the very hard to develop skills gained in formal education such as knowledge of research, mathematical and natural science skills, information retrieval skills and analytical thinking. Also the foundations for learning the skills are set out in formal education after which it is likely that further development of skills through work experience is easier.

While the differences of development the skills differ quite little between formal education and work experience, the differences highlight the importance of both factors in producing high-quality graduates in the field of technology. Many categories develop somewhat identically through both education and work experience but the differences are what matter the most. Formal education clearly lays the groundwork for further development by improving the core skills in the field of technology: mathematical and natural science skills, information retrieval and analytical thinking to highlight a few. Work experience also play a very important role by compensating where formal studies are fumbling: practical application of theories, attitude towards developing own skills and leadership skills to name a few.

4 EMPLOYABILITY OF GRADUATES

The Finnish M.Sc.'s in the field of technology gain on average over 2 years of work experience during their studies. However, the total study time of the respondents is approximately seven years with the target total study time being five years. According to the TEK Graduate Survey, the studies are delayed due to many reasons such as lack of motivation and lack of support and guidance in thesis work and/or studies. However the most common reason for delay in studies is working while studying.

Working alongside of studies provides a wide range of advantages for the students as explained in chapter 1. In addition to what we covered in chapter 1, work experience is also a source of motivation for studying as students get a better perspective and understanding on what kind of a career they would like to pursue. Working while studying also helps choosing courses and whole majors or minors according to interests discovered through work experience. Another perk of working alongside studies is that higher education degrees include mandatory or optional traineeships for which students also get study credits for.

The average 2 years of work experience is gained cumulatively throughout the studies. It is very common for the students to work during the summerbreak. Universities tend to provide some courses for summer for the students that fail landing a summer job or prefer studying in the summer. Spending the summer studying is however quite often a backup plan for students: in the summer of 2016, 82 % of students in the field of technology were employed. Students also work quite a lot during the semesters with 53 % of students in the field of technology working at least occasionally during semesters in the academic year 2015-2016. The summer jobs tend to be full-time and jobs during semesters tend to be part-time. (TEK Student Survey 2016) The M.Sc. thesis in the field of technology is mostly conducted in employment which also

contributes an average of 8 months to the work experience of graduates. Only 19 % of 2016 graduates received no compensation for their masters thesis and 54 % conducted their thesis in the industry.

Finnish M.Sc.'s in Technology and Architects are mostly already employed when they graduate as seen in Fig. 3. The rate of employment is even higher if we account for agreed but not yet signed job contracts at the time of graduation. The total average rate of employment of graduates in 2016 was 68 % including the agreed job contracts. Fig. 3 also highlights the importance of work experience in enhancing the employability of graduates: the more work experience the graduate has gained during studies, the more likely they are to be employed at the time of graduation.

Fig. 3. Employment and amount of work experience (excluding M.Sc. Thesis work) gained during studies of M.Sc. in Tech graduates in 2016. (TEK Graduate Survey 2016)

One of the advantages of gaining work experience prior to graduation is the reduced transition time from education to work. As seen in Fig. 4, the Finnish average transition time from tertiary education to work is the seventh fastest of the EU-27 comparison (Finland average 3.5 months vs. EU-27 average 5.1 months). The reason for the swift employment after graduation is explained to a large extent by the fact that graduates get employed to the organization where they have worked during studies as seen in Fig. 5. More than three out of four employed graduates have worked during studies in the same organization where they were employed at the time of graduation.

Notes: Results are based on people who left formal education in the last five years.
 BG, LT and SI data lack reliability due to low sample sizes for the category "at most lower secondary".

Fig. 4. Average length of transition from school to work by educational attainment level (Finland = FI), fields of science combined 2009. (Eurostat)

Fig. 5. Previous relation with employer, employed graduates 2016. (TEK Graduate Survey 2016)

The graduates also feel that the first position after graduation corresponds very well with their educational background. Four out of five think that job corresponds either well or very well both with the graduates' field of studies and level of education. Due to intensive culture of working during studies, graduates tend to skip the trainee phase of employment after graduation as it is already taken care of alongside studies.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper we focused our study of work experience and employability in the graduates of engineering and technology. The amount of work experience gained during studies has a strong effect on the employability of graduates.

The Finnish higher education policy aims for shorter length of studies to lengthen the careers of graduates. That however seems highly unnecessary according to our data. The professional careers of graduates in the field of engineering and technology start already in the course of studies. The co-ops, CDIO concepts and traineeships are and can be embedded in the engineering degrees through recognition of the skills and competencies gained outside of the classroom.

REFERENCES

[1] Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland TEK, Graduate Feedback Survey 2016, <https://www.tek.fi/fi/uutishuone/tutkimukset/vastavalmistuneiden-palautekysely>

[2] Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland TEK, Student Survey 2016, <https://www.tek.fi/fi/uutishuone/tutkimukset/opiskelijatutkimus>

[3] Eurostat, School to work transition statistics, http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Archive:School-to-work-transition_statistics&oldid=119868

[4] Hallituksen strateginen ohjelma <http://80.248.162.139/osaaminenjakoulutus/korkeakoulutus/index.html>

[5] The Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture: Opetuksen ja tutkimuksen kehittämissuunnitelma, <https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/79100/opm09.pdf?sequence=1>

[6] The Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture: Koulutus ja tutkimus vuosina 2011-2016, http://80.248.139/exports/sites/default/OPM/koulutuspolitiikka/asiakirjat/Kesu_2011_2016_fi.pdf